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Research

Mantra Reciting (*Parit*) in Burmese Buddhists

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Abstract: The term “*parit*” in Myanmar is derived from Pāli word ‘*paritta*’ in accordance with the rule of omitting final syllable (*uttaralopa*). Actually, the *paritta* discourses are the *suttas* preached by the Buddha for the purpose of keeping as an enclosure to be free from troubles and dangers. These *suttas* are the most popular and handiest ones among lay people. They recite *Parit* every day to get blessing, to be in safe, to not to get disturbing from evils or devils. The *paritta*-recitation and listening to it can be regarded as religious activities in Theravada Buddhist countries. Whenever they have matters, they usually ask *Samgha* (monks) to come and recite the *paritta*. Items such as flowers (*parittamala*), sand (*parittavāluka*), thread (*parittasuttaka*) and water (*paritta-udaka*) are put in front of the monks reciting the *paritta*. It is believed by the Buddhism that these things such as flowers, sand, thread and water are left behind with powers and orders of the *paritta* and can protect from various troubles and dangers. Then *paritta*-sand and *paritta*-thread are usually put in the compound of their house, *paritta*-flowers are put on the walls of their house and young kids are worn with *paritta*-thread as necklace to keep away from danger or evil spirit.

Keywords: Buddhist Bible, *parit*, *Paritta* reciting, Buddhist Mantra.

The meaning of the term “*Paritta*”

Paritta comes from *Pari*√*tā*. ‘*Pari*’ is a prefix, meaning ‘round about’ and according to ‘*tā pālāne*’, √*tā* is in the sense of *pālāne* ‘safeguard, protect or defend’¹.

¹ *aggavaṃsa*, 1960, 225.

According to the Pali description, “Parittanti mahātejavantataya samantato sattanam bhayam upaddavam upasagganca tayati rakkhatiti parittam²” it is so name paritta because of having great powers to protect all kinds of creature from any kinds of danger.

According to the Pali description, “paribhayam tayatiti parittam parisamantato bhayam tayati rakkhatiti parittam”, paritta can protect all sorts of evil coming from any kinds of direction. Thus, Buddhists believe reciting of paritta mantra can protect them from dangers and give them blessing and prosperous. Generally, there are eleven suttas regarded as the paritta in Myanmar. Eleven Parittas in Myanmar are as follow,

1. Maṅgala Sutta (Discourse on Blessings)
2. Ratana Sutta (The jewel Discourse)
3. Metta Sutta (Loving kindness)
4. Khandha Sutta (Discourse of Five aggregates)
5. Mora Sutta (The peacock’s prayer for protection)
6. Vaṭṭa Sutta (The Quail’s prayer for protection)
7. Dhajagga Sutta (The Banner Discourse)
8. Aṭanaṭiya Sutta (Discourse on Aṭanaṭiya)
9. Aṅgulimala Sutta (Discourse of Aṅgulimala)
10. Bojjhaṅga Sutta (Discourse of Bojjhaṅga)
11. Pubbaṅga Sutta (Discourse of constellation)

This collection of paritta discourses “Paritta Potha” is the most widely known work in Myanmar. It is called The Buddhist Bible; it is given an important place in the Buddhist home, and is even treated with veneration. Some have committed to memory the three well-known discourses. Maṅgalasutta, Ratanasutta and Mettasutta. Even children are familiar with these discourses, for they learn them from their parents and elders or from “the dhamma schools”. It is customary for Buddhist monks, when they are invited to the homes of the laity on occasions of domestic importance, such as birth days, house-warming, illness and similar events to recite the three popular discourses mentioned above. In the domestic and social life of the people of Sri Lanka, paritta ceremony is of great significance. No festival or function, religious or social is complete without the recital of the paritta.

On special occasions, monks are invited to recite the paritta not for short periods but right through the night or for three or seven days and at times, for weeks on such occasions a pavilion is constructed for the purpose of accommodating the monk at the recital. Before the

² aggavaṃsa, 1960,225.

commencement of the recital the laity present the ceremony makes a formal invitation to the monks by reciting in Pāli three stanzas which explain the purpose of the recital. Then the monks generally about twelve or fourteen, who have been invited, will recite. Then the monks generally about twelve or fourteen, who have been invited, will recite the three popular suttas. Thereafter a pair of monks will commence reciting the remaining sutta for two hours. They will then retire and will be followed by another pair for another two hours. Two monks must be constantly officiating. In this manner, the recital will last till dawn. While the recital continues there will be found a pot of water placed on a table before the monks. On this table there is also a sacred thread. For all night paritta ceremony the casket containing a relic of the Buddha and the Parit Potha or the book of protection are also brought into the pavilion. The relic represents the Buddha, the Parit Potha represents the Dhamma or the teaching of the Buddha and the reciting Bhikkhusaṅgha represent the Ariyasamgha or the Arahants.

The thread is drawn round the interior of the pavilion and its end twisted round the casket, the neck of the pot of water, and tied to the cord of the book. While the special discourses are being recited the monks hold the thread. The purpose is to maintain an unbroken communication from the water to relic to the Paritta Potha and to the officiating monks, (Buddha, Dhamma, Saṅgha, the Ti-ratana, the three jewels) A ball of thread connected to the Three jewels, and the water is unloosened and passed on to the listeners (seated on the ground or mats), who hold the thread while the recital goes on.

When the recital in Pāli of the entire book is over at dawn, the thread sanctified by the recital is divided into pieces and distributed among the devotees to be tied round their wrists or necks. At the same time the sanctified water is sprinkled on all, who even drink a little of it and sprinkle it on their head. These are to be regarded as symbols of the protective power of the paritta that was recited.

Summary of Eleven Parittas- Maṅgala sutta

The Maṅgala sutta includes in the Kuddakapath and Suttanipata. Maṅgala means prosperous, development. It is described in many ways:

- (i) “Maṅganti satta etena vuddhiṃ gacchantiti Maṅgalaṃ”- According to this description, the word “maṅgala” derived from Maṅg + ala.
- (ii) Maṅgalanti mahanti imehi sattahi maṅgalani iddhiṃ vuddhiṃ ca papunantiti attho”-By practicing this doctrine, one can get fulfilment, and wealth.
- (iii) “Maṅgam papaṃ lunāti chindatīti Maṅgalaṃ”.

It can get rid of evil things which can reach to hell. So it is called “maṅgala”. According to this description, maṅgala is maṅga + Lu + a Maṅga means hell. Lu means ‘to cut’. In accordance with the definition mentioned above, the Maṅgalasutta is a paritta which destroys the evil things and develops the good things. Nobody knew about the auspiciousness until the Buddha preached it. So, auspiciousness was thought on their own accord. They thought that seeing the good things was Diṭṭhamaṅgala, hearing the good voice was Sutamaṅgala and getting good smell and tastes was Mutamaṅgala. Many deities and men have pondered upon just what blessings were. Then a certain deity was sent to address to Blessed One. So the deity came to the Blessed one. The Blessed One was dwelling at Jetavana monastery. thus, the Blessed One preached the blessings³. These blessing are not only to read but also to follow practically for everybody. Anyone who recites and follows the blessings can get worldly wealth. According to the commentary, one who practices the blessings can attain nirvana.

The thirty-eight blessings are as follows:

1. Asevana ca bālānaṃ = not to associate with fools
2. Paṇḍitānaṃ sevana = to associate with the wise
3. Pūjā ca pūjaneyyanaṃ = to honour those who are worthy of honour
4. Patirūpadesavāso ca = to live in a suitable place
5. Pubbe ca katapuññata = to have done meritorious deeds in the past
6. Attasammāpaṇidhi ca = to keep one’s mind and body in a proper way
7. Bahusaccaṅca = to have much learning
8. Sippañca = to have much learning
9. Vinayo ca susikkhito = to be well-trained in moral conduct
10. Subhasita ca ya vāca = to have speech that is well spoken
11. Mātu upaṭṭhānaṃ = rendering thanks to mother
12. Pitu upaṭṭhanaṃ = rendering thanks to father
13. Puttadārassa saṅgaho = supporting children and wife
14. Anākulā ca kammanta = having work that causes no confusion
15. Dāñña ca = giving
16. Dhammacariyā ca = practice of what is good
17. Ñatakāñanca saṅgaho = support of one’s relatives
18. Anavajjāni kammani = blameless actions

³Khu. tṭha I. 1958, 104-130

19. Ārati virati papa = abstention from evil in mind, in body and speech
20. Majjapānā ca saṃyamo = abstention from intoxicants
21. Appamādo ca dhammesu = non-negligence in meritorious acts
22. Gāravo ca = respectfulness
23. Nivāto ca = humbleness
24. Santuṭṭhi ca = contentment
25. Kataññutā = gratitude
26. Kālena dhammassavanaṃ = listening to the Dhamma on suitable occasions
27. Khantī ca = patience
28. Sovacassatā = obedience
29. Samañānañca dassanaṃ = meeting those who have calmed the mental defilements
30. Kalena dhammasākaccha = discussing the Dhamma on suitable occasions
31. Tapo ca = self-control
32. Brahmācariyañca = practice a noble life
33. Ariyasaccāna dassanaṃ = seeing the Noble truth
34. Nibbānasacchikiriyā ca = realization of nibbana
35. Phuṭṭhassa lokadhammehi cittaṃ yassa na kampaṭi = The mind of a person who is confronted with worldly condition does not flutter
36. Asokaṃ = sorrowless
37. Virajaṃ = dustless
38. Khemaṃ = secure

The other works count 38 kinds of blessing thus;

Matāpitu Upaṭṭhānam = rendering thanks to one's parent

Āratī pāpā = Abstaining from bad deeds mentally

Viratī pāpā = Abstaining from bad deeds physically

One who practices these blessings cannot be conquered by his enemies in the present life and will not be influenced in future. He will be free from dangers. Having done as here directed, being undefeated everywhere and attain happiness everywhere, said by the Buddha.

Ratanasutta

The Ratana Sutta is found in the Kuddakapāṭha and Suttanipāṭa. Ratana means jewel. In the accounts of Ratanasutta, there were sacred treasure of Buddha, Dhamma and Saṃgha. In this account of the first stanza of 'Panidhānato paṭṭhāya' showed the glory of the imagination of Ven-Ananda. This stanza was not preached by the Buddha but the ancient teachers had mentioned to honour the paritta. The Ratanasutta is the verse beginning with "Yanīdha

bhūtāni”. There is no introduction on why the Ratanasutta was preached in the Kuddakapāṭha. It is found only in the Kuddakapāṭha Aṭṭhakathā.

The Buddha was invited to Vesālī because there were starving, troubles of diseases and cruelty of devils. When the Buddha arrived, the devils ran away. The Buddha stood at the door of the city and told Ven-Ananda together with a Licchavi prince to recite the Ratanasutta between third floors of the city wall.

Ven-Ānanda took the Buddha’s bowl filled with water and thrown the water all over the city reciting the Ratanasutta. In this way, the enemy of the devils and disease were disappeared. That is shown in the Khuddakapāṭha Atthakathā. The Ratanasutta is denoted made asseveration trust with the astonishing honourable glory of three jewels.

Mettasutta

The Mettasutta includes in the Kuddakapāṭha⁴ and Itivuttaka⁵. Metta is mental factor of loving-kindness and wishes for all beings welfare. It forms by helping for the good of others. It forms in the mind of religious practice as he gets rid of grudge. It is a right attitude to see from the bright side the others. Right thinking is closed to loving-kindness.

Mettā is peace and tranquility. Mental factor of loving-kindness is broad-minded, and boundless. It has no anger and no wish to destroy. Cease of malevolence is the completion of loving-kindness. Loving with gehassitapema (love concerning the house) is destruction of loving-kindness. Getting rid of malevolence is special profit of loving-kindness. It has the sign of helping for the benefit of other.

The Mettasutta was preached by the Buddha to five hundred monks. The cause of teaching this sutta is as follows: While the Buddha was staying at Savatthi, a band of monks, having received subjects of meditation from the master, proceeded to a forest to spend the rainy season. The tree-deities in inhabiting this forest were worried by their arrival, as they had to descend from tree abode and dwell on the ground. They hoped the monks would leave soon, but they found out that the monks would stay the whole rainy period. Then, they harassed them in diverse ways, during the night they haunted the monks using frightening appearance, noise and smell to scare away.

Living under such conditions being impossible, the monks went to the Master and informed him of their difficulties. Thereon the Buddha instructed them the Mettasutta and advised them to return the previous place, and let them equip with this sutta for their protection. The monks went back to forest, and practiced the instruction conveyed, permeated

⁴ Khu tṭha I, 1958,132-167

⁵ Khu I, 1958,205.

the whole atmosphere with their radiant thoughts of metta or loving-kindness. The deities so affected by this power of love, hence forth allowed them to mediate peacefully.

The discourse gets divided into two parts. The first detailing the standard of moral conduct required by one who wishes to attain purity and peace and the second the method of practice of metta.

Before cultivating of loving- kindness, one should complete the following practices:

1. Sakko – ability to work out his own
2. Uju – must be honest, must be upright
3. Suhuju – must be upright in mental conduct
4. Suvaco – must be easy to admonish
5. Mudu – must not be proud extremely
6. Anatimānī – must be content
7. Subharo – must be easy to support
8. Subharo – must be easy to support
9. Appakicco – must be little duties
10. Sallahukavutti – must be simple livelihood
11. Santandriya – must be calm in all faculties
12. Nipako – must be prudent
13. Appagabbho – must be gentle in physical and mental conducts
14. Kulesu ananugiddho – not hanker after association with families
15. Na ca khuddamacare kinci yena vinnu pare upavadeyyum – should not do a little evil deed which can be rebuke by the wise.

The second is the method of practice of Metta.

There are 17 kinds of living beings to share the loving- kindness. The Buddha preached the verse beginning with “ye keci panabhutatthi”

1. Tasa – feeble (the seeker)
2. Thavara – strong (arahant)
3. Diṭṭha – those seen
4. Adiṭṭhā – those dwelling far
5. Dure -those dwelling far
6. Avidure – those dwelling near
7. Bhuta – those who are to recircle in samsara
8. Sambhavesī – those who are not to recircle in samsara
9. Dīgha – those who are long

10. Rassa – those who are short
11. Majjhima – Those who are medium size (not long or short)
12. Mahantā -those who are large
13. Anuka – those who are small
14. Majjhima – those who are medium size, not large and small
15. Thūlā – those who are round and thick
16. Anukā – those who are small and thin
17. Majjhimā – those who are medium size not round or thin.

After that the Blessed One preached “the desire of wise” with the verse beginning with “Na paro paraṃ nikuppetha”. “Let him not deceive nor despise anyone, anywhere, in anger or ill- will. Let him not wish another ill. Just as a mother would protect her only child throughout her life, so let one cultivate a boundless love towards all beings. Let him radiate boundless love towards the entire world-above, below, and across unhindered, without ill-will, without enmity. One should cultivate loving-kindness mindfully in all department, reclining, sitting, standing and walking. It is the ‘holy living preached by the Buddha’. Because of the profit of the cultivation of loving- kindness, one cannot get wrong view (micchādiṭṭhi) and endowed with the holy Enlightenment so he who detaches all craving from sensuality, never get to the inception of the rebirth process, preached by the Buddha.

Khandhasutta

The Khandhasutta includes in the Cūlavagga, the Aṅguttara and the Jātaka. In accordance with “Attabhāvasañkhātāṃ khandhapañcakamparisamantato tāyati rakkhatīti khandha parittam”, it is called Khandhaparitta because the aggregate would be guarded and protected from the dangers of every side. The Khandhasutta was preached by the Buddha with reference to a monk who was bitten by the snake and passed away at the Jetavana monastery. Four kinds of dragons, namely Virūpakkha, Erāpatha, Chabyāputta and Kaṇhāgotamaka are mentioned in the Khandhasutta. By reciting the Khandhasutta, one can be free from dangers of not only dragons and snakes but also tigers, lions, leopards and wild animals. The Buddha exhorted to share loving-kindness to four kinds of dragons, no-legged animals, two legged animals and many legged animals. In this sutta, the power of loving-kindness and virtues of the three holy jewels are used as protection.

Morasutta⁶

The Morasutta includes in the story of Mora, a king peacock.

⁶ Ja I, 1961,228

It was called Moraparitta because it protected king peacock from all directions so that he could live safely. The Buddha uttered this Moraparitta, with reference to a monk, wanted to return to the life of a householder because he was assailed by thoughts associated with the senses.

In that sutta king peacock that was gold in color, seeing the sun in the early morning, made protection by reciting the verse beginning with “Upetayam” and then he usually goes out to search food. Therefore, he got his food easily against dangerous snares. Also in the evening when the sun set he could go for a sleep because of protection of the verse beginning with “Apetayam”.

In this *paritta* king peacock paid respect to the sun and wished for safety at the times of setting and rising of the sun. After that, he paid homage to those Buddhas, who have understood and realized all things. Then he wished for looking after him from those Buddhas. Moreover, he paid homage to Enlightenment and five kinds of deliverance (*vimutti*).

King Peacock could live peacefully away from dangers such paying homage to the sun, the Buddha (the Enlightened One), Dhamma (Teachings of the Buddha), Saṅgha (Monks) as the refuge. In the Morasutta, there are two categories of verses: one to recite in the morning (when the sun rises) and one to do in the evening (when the sun sets).

That fact is stated by following words already mentioned in the Morasutta:

Udeti = (the sun) rises (from the east)

Divasam = the whole day

Apeti = (the sun) sets (towards the west)

Rattim = the whole night.

By reciting the Morasutta, it is sure one can live and stay peacefully both days and nights in one's life being away from the dangers.

Vaṭṭasutta

The Vaṭṭasutta includes in the Jātaka and Cariyāpitaka. It is called Vaṭṭaparitta, because it protected from forest-fire to the little quail (the future Buddha). The Blessed One related the story of fulfilling virtues in his past (Cariyapitaka) at the request of Venerable Mahamoggalana. The Vattajataka is one of the practice containing in the Cariyapitaka. The quail (the future Buddha) was perfected with the practice for making asseveration of truth, put out the forest-fire as it dropped into the water. According to the Jataka, the Vattaparitta was preached to other monks by the Buddha. But it is not all verses from the Vattasutta but one verse, which is beginning with “Santi pakkha apatana”.

At one time the Blessed One visited to Magadha with his disciples. In a certain forest, they came across the forest-fire. The forest-fire went around far away from the Buddha. So the monks admired him wonderfully. Then the Blessed One said, “the forest-fire can never burn this place because of the power of truth that I have done in the previous life”. And then the Buddha expounded the Vattajataka. The Blessed One claimed the place where the king of quail (the future Buddha) made the asseveration of the truth as, “it can never be burnt as long as this world exists by reciting the verse beginning with “kappatthyim mahatejam”.

In the Vattaparitta, the first two verses are the praise of paritta. As safeguard recital, the Vattasutta begins with “Atthi loke silaguno”, but there are seven verses before “Atthi loke” which was preached to Venerable Mahamoggallana. It is likely to be that the old wise selected the verses which contains the essence of doctrines as paritta.

The little quail made asseveration of truth thus:

“Oh wildfire, I have a pair of wing to fly away, but they are unmatured. I have two legs to run out, but they are unmatured, my parents left out me in the nest they flew away for their lives, “Oh wildfire go away from me”. After making his asseveration of truth, the wildfire was extinguished as it dropped into the water. Making the asseveration of truth of the small quail is that, being an unmatured bird, who could not fly away although he had wings and legs and he was abandoned by his parents. Those happenings are truth. So it is saccā. In making the asseveration of truth, things are not principle, but true things are. The Blessed One expounded thus: there are no things as equal as Truth and the power of his making asseveration truth remained as the fulfillment of good deeds”.

Dhajaggasutta⁷

The *Dhajaggasutta* includes in the Sagathāvaggasamyutta. According to the definition “Dhajaggaṃ ādiṃ desitam parittam dhajagga parittam”, it is also called Dhajaggaparitta. It is preached originating the tip of the banner. As Sakka (lord of the gods) instructed the gods to look up at the banners not to be frightened, so also the Buddha exhorted his monks who are going to take meditation session either in the forest or in a silent place, to remember and recite attributes of the Three Gems: Buddha, Dhamma and Saṅgha.

Moreover, the Buddha said that there not privates looking up at banners representing the divine kings- Sakka, Pajāpati, Varuna and Īsāna might be able to wipe out their fright fear or they might not: for even there spiritual kings, the Sakka, Pajāpati, Varuṇa and Īsāna themselves, usually have fear of fright.

⁷Sam I, 1957,220.

The Buddha has preached that those monks who repeatedly recite attributes of the Three Gems “Buddha, Dhamma and Saṅgha” would really wipe out any kind of fears. In the Dhajaggasutta, the Buddha has explained about nine kinds of attributes of the Buddha; six kinds of attributes of the Dhamma and nine kinds of attributes of the Saṅgha.

Aṭānaṭīyasutta

The Aṭānaṭīyasutta includes in the Pāthikavagga⁸ of the Dīghanikaya.

Although there are 500 verses in the Pathikavagga, the ancient scholars selected six verses and arranged with other glorious gatha as paritta. The Atanatiyasutta was applied to the Buddha by Vessavanna, the king of gods. He applied to keep this as paritta to protect from cruel demons. The Aṭānaṭīyasutta prays seven preceding Buddhas called Vipassi, Sikhi, Vessabhu, Kakusandha, Konagamana and Gotama and describes the unique gratitude of Buddha. It also honours the 32 great signs, the 80 small signs and the six rays of the Buddha. It made a wish to look after all the creatures by the Buddha and the Gandhabba god in the east, the Kumbhanda god in the south, the Dragon god from the west and the monster god from the north. In addition, Dhatarattha, the god who lives in the east of Mt.Meru, Virulhaka, the god from the south, Virupakkha, the god from the west, Kuvera, the god from the north are requested to look after all the creatures. And also prays that the gods of heaven (Akasathadevata), the gods of earth (Bhummatthadevata) and the other good-mannered deities may look after all the creatures. We may be free from dangers and diseases and we may live long.

At the end of Atanatiyasutta, it concluded that all the person who respect and pay attention to the elders, glorious persons and oldest persons will be live long, good-looking structure, wealthy and strong as the equal result. In Atanatiyasutta, the six gathas beginning with “Vipassissa ca namatthu” are the verses which are selected from the Pathikavagga. The twenty one verses beginning with “Etena saccena sambuddha” were preached by Mahaviharavasi Thera. The last gatha beginning with “Abhivandana” is selected from the Dhammapada which was preached to Ayuvaddhana”. Because of preaching in the Aṭānaṭīya forest monastery, is so called “Aṭānaṭīyasutta”. In other words, the god king of Aṭānaṭīya city applied and requested this sutta, so it was called “Aṭānaṭīyaparitta”.

Aṅgulimalasutta

The *Aṅgulimalasutta* includes in the Majjhimapaṇṇāsa. The Aṅgulimalasutta was called after the name of Aṅgulimala (fingers garland). At a certain time, while residing at the Jetavana

⁸ Dī III , 1956,159.

monastery, the Buddha uttered the Angulimalasutta, with reference to the expectant mother who was in difficulty to give birth. While going around for his alms-food, Ven- Angulimala heard the voice of expectant mother who was in difficulty to give birth. He felt a great pity on her and reported it to the Buddha, saying “All living beings who are in existence of unending cycle of rebirth suffer and face with difficulty”.

The Buddha taught the paritta to Venarable Angulimala and sent him there to recite it near the woman who could not give birth. Venerable Angulimala recited the paritta near the expectant mother. Instantly, she gave birth to the child with great ease. From that time on, Ven-Angulimala was believed and revered by the people as a monk who could give peace and wealth to the people. As a result, he was offered things by people and was free from dangers such as cursing, throwing with knives and stones. The Buddha made him recite the paritta hoping that he could sit for meditation without worrying about the alms food. Although he sat for meditation, he did not get any concentration power and could see the visions of killing people in his past. The Blessed One knew that he can ignore his evil deeds in the past and he would cultivate meditation.

The Angulimalasutta is useful not only for giving birth easily but also for protection every danger. So it is commented as Mahaparitta in the commentary. Ven-Angulimala, himself was free from dangers and he was prosperous. Only then he attained Nibbāna (Liberation, ultimate goal of Buddhism). Even an animal which had difficulty to give birth could give birth easily, when it was put on that bench, on which the Thera made the asseveration truth or the washing water from that bench was pound on the animal which could not give birth, could do easily. In the commentary, it was said that as long as the world exists, the power of the place where Ven. Aṅgulimala made an asseveration of truth remains.

Bojjhaṅgasutta

The seven kinds of *Bojjhaṅga* are found in the Khandavagga of the Samyutta Nikaya. There is no direct expression of Bojjhaṅgasutta in the Pali canon. It is named Bojjhaṅgasutta for the seven kinds of Bojjhaṅga which can achieve the wisdom of Arahatta also can protect any diseases and illness. As the Bojjhaṅgasutta is in prose, it may be composed by former scholars.

In the Bojjhaṅgasutta, it is vowed the truth that if is person repeatedly matures through meditation the seven kinds of Bojjhaṅga namely: Satisambhojjhanga, Dhammavijayasambhojjhanga, Viriyasambhojjhanga, Pitisambhojjhanga, Passaddhisambhojjhanga, Samadisambhojjhanga, Upekkhasambhojjhanga, he will achieve

Nibbana (liberation). Due to this truth, there will be no danger forever and excellent auspiciousness will be achieved.

The Buddha preaches seven kinds of Bojjhanga to Ven- Mahamoggallana who is seriously ill while living at Mt. Gijjhakuta; and also to Ven- Mahakassapa who is also seriously ill while living at Pippali cave. Due to this doctrine, their illness has been totally wiped out as there can be no water on a lotus leaf. So it is vowed the truth that there will be no danger auspiciousness will be achieved. When the Buddha himself becomes ill, He asked Ven- Cunda to recite the Bojjhangesutta and with care and satisfaction he listens to it: then he gets his recovery. Due to this truth, there will be no danger forever and excellent auspicious will be achieved. As the Buddha, Ven- Mahamoggallana and Ven- Mahakassapa get total recovery from their illness as they could abandon kilesa (evil desire) with meditation. Due to this truth there will be no danger forever and excellent auspiciousness will be achieved.

Pubbanhasutta

The last three and half verses of the *Pubbanhasutta* beginning with “Sunakkhattam” are verses preached by the Buddha in the *Anguttaranikaya*. Among the other verses, verses starting with “yam kinci vittam” are also preached by the Buddha in the *Ratanasutta* of the *Suttanipata*. Apart from these, the remaining ones are verses arranged by preachers of older time; not by the Buddha. Then the whole sutta is called *Pubbanhasutta* due to the composition of verses in *Pubbanhasutta*. It is so named *Pubbanhasutta* for auspicious words are being composed. In the *Pubbanhasutta*, it said as a wish that due to the power and authority of Great Buddha, Great Law (Doctrine) and Great Samgha (Buddhist monk community), all kinds of evil omens, unsuspectingness, unpleasant sound of evil birds, bad constellation, and night mares would be able to be wiped out.

Then the verse beginning with “dukkhapatta ca niddukkha” is a verse of sending loving-kindness for those who are poor, to free from poverty; for those who are in trouble to be free from trouble; for those who are in worry and anxiety, to be free from those things. The verse beginning with “Etthavata ca amhehi” is the one sending loving-kindness to celestial beings. The verse starting with “Sabbe Buddha” is a formation of the paritta enclosure due to the power of the Buddhas and Paccekabuddhas who are full of physical and mental strength; to the power of Arahants. Verses starting with “yam kinci” are adopted from *Ratanasutta* and it is an expression that the three Gems: the Buddha, the Law (Doctrine) and the Samgha (Buddhist monk community) are of great value than other gems from this world, the states of dragons and Garuda (Grove), the states of celestial beings (gods and Brahmas). The three

Gems of the Buddha, the Dhamma and the Samgha are mysteriously excellent and pleasant; and due to these sincere words, let every creature be rich and prosperous.

The verse beginning with “Bhavatu” is a verse of sending wish meaning to let every good and auspicious event happen; to let every spirits guard and due to the power of paritta, let every creature be rich physically and mentally. The verse beginning with “Mahakaruniko” expresses that the Buddha had achieved different intellect and wisdom of Arahatta and Sabbannuta for he has practiced different principal virtues for the sake of every being. Due to this true sayings, let you be rich at every time.

The two verses starting with “Jayanto” and “Aparajitapallanke” are wishing ones describing that just as the Buddha has succeeded every enemy on the Aparajita throne; so also you succeed or get through troubles and dangers. Just as the Buddha who has achieved enlightenment on the Aparajita throne becomes satisfied, so also you become higher in standard. From verses beginning with “Sunakkhattam” to those with “Saha sabbehi ñatibhi” are adopted from the Aṅguttanikaya and they are actually Pubbaṅhasutta preached by the Buddha. In these verses, it is mentioned that the period of doing good deed is a good period, with good constellation and auspiciousness: he can get up well and every time is a good time for him. According to the commentary, those who practice good deeds always have good constellation, good auspiciousness and good period. There is no bad constellation for them. It is not necessary to check up one’s chance to follow an astrologer’s advice. But it is necessary to practice good deeds.

On the days, a certain people practice good deeds, their physical and mental performance are good, great and grand. It can be said that they put their fortune on the good deed. In this way, they practice good deeds and achieve good outcome. During the Buddha sāsanā, they together with their relative would become rich and free from any diseases or illness.

Conclusion

The parittas may be regarded as the most familiar Buddhist literature for any Buddhist in any place when Buddhism becomes prominent. According to the eleven parittas, sacca (faithfulness or sincerity), living with the rules of auspiciousness (maṅgala), approaching three kinds of gems (Buddha, Dhamma and saṅgha), practicing metta (love to all beings) are means of freedom from danger and fear. Since Buddhism introduced in Myanmar, the habit of Paritta – recitation has originated. The recitation of Parittas and listening to the Parittas are wide- spread throughout Myanmar in every age. The Parittas are essential in every religious and some social ceremonies.

In the Maṅgalasutta, the 38 blessings for a beatific life are used as means of freedom from dangers. Not only for recitation, but in real practice, one can achieve both benefits of lokiya (worldly affairs) and lokuttara (the way to escape from worldly desires and attachments). By praising the great honour and benefits of the three Gems, the Pubbaṅhasutta, Bojjhangasutta, Ratanasutta, Dhajaggasutta and Aṭanaṭiyasutta are used as means of freedom from dangers. According to the Mettasutta and Khandhasutta, practicing love can secure dangers. Reciting an oath of truth or faithfulness can be free from danger according to the Angulimalasutta, Morasutta and Vaṭṭasutta. In conclusion, the parittas may be regarded as ancient Buddhist literature and the most familiar with the Buddhists.

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